

ISSN: 2822-1850

SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMSS)

SJMSS

Volume 2, Issue 1, 2022

SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMSS)

Published by St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Kathmandu, Nepal

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMSS)

Editor-in-Chief

Fr. Augustine Thomas, S.J. (PhD)
Principal, *St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Nepal*

Associate Editor

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari (PhD)
Head of Research,
Research office of Management and Social Sciences
(ROOMS)
St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Nepal

Editorial Board

Fr. Jiju Varghese, S.J. Director
Richard Callahan (Professor)
Shasidhar Belbase (PhD)
Prakash C Bhattarai (PhD)

SXC Loyala Campus, Nepal
University of San Francisco, USA
United Arab Emirates University, UAE
Kathmandu University, Nepal

SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMSS)

Published by St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Kathmandu, Nepal

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Reviewers for this Volume 2, Issue 1, 2022

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari

Dil Bahadur Gurung

Fr. Jiju Varghese, S.J.

Samantha Maris

Surya Prasad Subedi

SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMS)

Published by St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Kathmandu, Nepal

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Table of Content

A Study on Religion and Everyday Life in Rural Setting <i>Sudhangsu Sekhar Datta</i>	1
Managing Organizational Crisis for performance, production, productivity and profitability <i>Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari and Mohini Shakya</i>	17
Determination of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of the Role of a Nurse in Achieving Universal Healthcare Coverage among Nurses in Level Three at Kenyatta National Hospital <i>Phyllis Kaingu</i>	28

SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJ MSS)

Published by St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Kathmandu, Nepal

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.